

TITLE: DNA inspired waveguide for reducing the SBS Threshold Power of Pump.

Fig: DNA inspired waveguide

Fig:Conventional Waveguide

Key equation:

$$P_{th} \propto 1 / (g * L_{eff})$$

Here, P=Threshold Power of Pump

L_eff= Interaction length

A)Dna inspired Waveguide:

- 1) High L_eff
- 2) Low P

B)Conventional waveguide:

- 1)Low L_eff

2) high P

Conclusion: Therefore by implementing the DNA inspired waveguide we can increase the effective interaction length (L_{eff}) that will eventually decrease the SBS threshold power of Pump (P).